

Review

China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI): The impact towards innovation development in Asian Countries

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Abstract: This study investigates the impact of China's Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) on national innovation systems, utilizing the Global Innovation Index (GII) as an analytical measure. Implementing a Staggered Difference-in-Differences (SDID) design, the research isolates BRI's effects on innovation performance, highlighting significant enhancements in GII rankings for partner countries, especially in Asia. The analysis underscores the role of targeted international investments in fostering innovation and economic growth, with pronounced benefits for lower and middle-income nations. The findings provide strategic insights for policymakers in forming global partnerships, emphasizing the BRI's influence on enhancing national innovation capabilities.

Keywords: Asia, BRI, China, GII, SDID.

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Introduction

Asia is the most populous region in the world, accounting for over 60% of the global population. Amid the global economic surge, each country in Asia is obligated to maintain economic growth while addressing political climate and natural challenges [1]. Since the late 20th century, countries in Asia such as Japan, Singapore, and China have been achieving many economic miracles, despite the huge obstacle placed on the geographical connectivity fueled by the lack infrastructure development [2]. To tackle many of these challenges, the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) was initiated in 2013 by the Chinese government as a reflection of the ancient Silk Road and to increase the overall development of many neighboring countries.

BRI has received much support since its establishment, as shown by more than 20 countries joining this program in the first three year of development. However, there are growing concerns about China's debt trap and military advancement, which overshadowing the economic and innovation development from this movement [3]. Even without the acknowledgment of many global powers, BRI continues to grow and reached USD 1,053 trillion by 2023, with 60% spent on construction contracts and 40% on non-financial investments [4].

Apart from economic and connectivity impacts, BRI is directed to amplify the rate of innovation in Asia. The commitment towards advancing the innovation performance of BRI partners was shown in The Special Plan for

Promoting the Scientific and Technological Innovation Cooperation of the Belt and Road Construction (PSTIC), jointly issued by the Ministry of Science and Technology and three other ministries of China [5]. To further understanding the impact of BRI investment towards partnering countries, a framework must be adopted to explain the complex system behind a national level innovation, mainly based on governmental policy, university activity, environmental challenges, and the relationship between components.

One of the most well-accepted frameworks to discuss this complex matter is National Innovation System (NIS) framework proposed by Freeman [6]. To further develop the NIS, this paper will integrate Global Innovation Index (GII) as an indexed measurement of a country innovation capability and effectiveness. According to Crespo and Crespo [7], the data from GII is commonly used in the field of national level innovation. The GII is an index published annually by World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO). The GII has some unique qualities, such as a large amount of data, simplification of input and output measurements, and inclusion of a country's system of interaction [8]. To date, the GII has included 132 countries in its list and consistently updating their report.

Many studies have already been conducted to shed light on the internal perspective of Chinese firms that lend a hand in BRI toward "partner country of BRI" [9, 10]. However, there remains a notable gap in understanding the external perspective of BRI's partner countries. This study addresses this gap by focusing on how international policies, particularly the BRI, influence the effectiveness of NIS in partner countries, as measured by the GII.

The central research question guiding this investigation is: How does participation in the BRI affect the GII rankings of partner countries and how much benefits that was received by Asian countries? By utilizing open-source data from the World Bank, WIPO, and BRI investments from 2011 to 2023, this study aims to provide a neutral and reliable analysis of the BRI's impact, contributing valuable insights into the broader implications of international policy on national innovation systems.

Literature Review

2.1. Mark of BRI in Asia

In September 2013, the BRI was publicly announced by President Xi in Kazakhstan and Indonesia. This moment marks China as a global super power and a declaration of political and financial revitalization. However, modern era seems to be reluctant towards the revival of the ancient silk road which connecting Afro-Eurasia with the global system. The after-effect of cold war, international political climate, and sanction keep holding back the growth of BRI [11]. Despite the external pressure, the commitment of Chinese government in applying the BRI project gets the approval of 13 country in the beginning of initiative, 21 countries after 3 year of establishment, and more than 70 countries in 2018 [12]. Nowadays, BRI is an umbrella term which occupied the act of exchanging goods and services; network of infrastructure reflected from the past, while accommodating the modern necessity and future possibility; and a semi-independent investment and financing activity [13]. The long-term planning of BRI is divided into "Belt" and "Road" which stand for land-based and sea-based trade route. The sheer scale of GDP project is equal with 64.2% of world's population and 38.8% of world's GDP. As the closest area, Asia will hypothetically receive greater benefit and bigger attention in BRI project. This argumentation is highly supported by the shifting economic gravity which gradually move closer to Asia and the tightly covered geographical link of BRI's partner country and project in Asia [13, 14].

Asia is a formidable global presence, especially in human and natural resources. However, studies reveal a paradox where abundant resources do not equate to economic growth, especially in developing nations. Research highlights a stark contrast in growth and resource availability between developed and developing countries, leading to the concept of the "Curse of Natural Resources" [15].

This curse is often attributed to factors like reduced technological accumulation and diversion of resources away from manufacturing [16]. On the other hand, another study suggests that there is a conflict of interest within their own country. A study conducted by Lotfalipour and Salehnia [17], shows that internal conflicts over resource management,

weak governance, corruption, and limited freedom of speech exacerbate this issue, resulting in economic stagnation, inequality, and diminished welfare.

The resource curse poses a significant risk in Asia, where many countries remain in the lower middle-income bracket, despite possessing abundant natural resources like minerals, oil, and gas [18, 19]. With the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), there is potential for overcoming this curse by enhancing connectivity and fostering innovation. The BRI can facilitate resource sharing and technological transfers, which are crucial for market growth, production sophistication, and efficient resource use. By emphasizing innovation, the BRI aims to stimulate economic growth, enhance job effectiveness, and reduce reliance on raw material exports, offering a pathway to break the cycle of the resource curse in Asia.

2.2. Global Innovation Index (GII)

The GII index was launched in 2007 by INSEAD (*Institut Européen d'Administration des Affaires*) and World Business Magazine. In the early development of GII (2007-2010), the indexed score range was between 1 and 7. After publishing 3 indexes, GII was adopted internationally through joint publication by Cornell University, INSEAD, and WIPO (World Intellectual Property Organization) [20]. From that point onward, the index values have been increased to 100, and the base indicator is accounted for by 80 indicators. GII annually ranks 129 countries, and since its establishment, Switzerland has consistently held the first rank through a combination of robust research and development, world-class institutions and education facilities, and conducive policies for innovation [21].

GII is calculated by scoring and finding the average scores of two sub-indices. The first one is the innovation input sub-index (IISI), which is mainly divided into institution, human capital and research, infrastructure, market sophistication, and business sophistication. Whereas the second indices called innovation output sub-index (IOSI), is mainly explains knowledge or educational level, technology output, and creative output [22]. IISI stands as the propeller of national innovation by providing the necessary environmental support that is conducive enough for innovation to flourish. Institutions will provide adequate talented individuals to increase the human capital and research capability of a country [23]. After the first link in the supply chain is fulfilled, the next weak link is to provide related infrastructure to fulfill the sophisticated demand in the market and business area. IOSI is the opposite of supply; it shows the pure capability of a country in producing creative outputs and mainstream technological output.

The combination of IISI and IOSI is projected to completely, or at the very least, represent the majority of the reasons behind an innovative country. The long list of indices of GII was also the main aspect behind the degree of difficulty in advancing innovation in a country. This difficulty is enhanced a few more times in the case of overtaking the rank of another country [24]. Countries with better preparation will always be a few steps ahead of their chasers, hence why the top few most innovative countries in the world are dominated by European and American countries [25].

2.3. National Innovation System (NIS)

A system is a combination of components, where the interaction and relation between those components are as important as the result and outcome of the system. To uncover the complex relationship between components in national-level data, a structured framework or theory must be applied. NIS is a response to the neo-classical approach of supply and demand, which drives economic movement [26]. This theory begins as an applicable side of the Schumpeterian-based theory of creative destruction, especially to show how innovation drives economic growth [27]. From the work of Cho and Park [28], the NIS comprises essential components like institutions, industry, policy and government, and network interactions. Institutions include universities, research bodies, and government agencies. The industry encompasses private firms, market sophistication, and small enterprises. Policy and government involve national policies and support, while network interactions cover collaborations and innovation clusters. This framework offers a comprehensive view of a nation's innovation ecosystem, allowing researchers to identify strengths and weaknesses and develop policies that promote innovation and economic growth. By examining these interactions, policymakers can design better educational programs and regulations that enhance technological advancement and market competitiveness [18, 29].

2.4. Relation Between GII and NIS

In order to develop innovation across the partnering countries, the BRI project extended the establishment of PSTIC. To completely observe the impact of BRI project, this study uses the GII as a variable source in order to representing NIS. Compared to other indexes GII has few advantages, such as: 1) the extensive amount of country data; 2) the clarity of IISI and IOSI in explaining reasonable outcomes; 3) the majority of the data is flat data, with only 5 using survey data; 4) there is an additional perspective, which is creative output [30]. However, the most important reason is the complementary between GII data and NIS framework, which can cover a very wide range of observational necessities. The national interaction aspect of NIS is effectively captured by the GII's IISI and IOSI, which dissect environmental and infrastructural factors influencing innovation [31]. International differences are explained by comparing human capital, infrastructure, and government policies across countries [32].

The GII provides a comprehensive understanding of specialization, competitiveness, and growth performance, allowing researchers to pinpoint a country's strengths and weaknesses. By analysing these conditions, researchers can assess competitiveness and predict growth performance. The robustness of GII data supports a wide range of observational needs, crucial for longitudinal studies requiring consistent, reliable data over time [20]. Additionally, the inclusion of creative output adds depth to the analysis, capturing innovation aspects often overlooked by other indices. This multifaceted approach makes the GII an exceptional tool for understanding the dynamics of national innovation systems and their impact on global competitiveness. The GII's broad data and perspective make it a preferred choice for evaluating the effects of initiatives like the Belt and Road Initiative on national innovation landscapes.

Data and Methodology

3.1. Methodology

To discern the effect of international policy, particularly the BRI on the effectiveness of NIS, a SDID quasi-experimental design was adopted because the relatively more robust result, and able to reduce the effect of contemporaneous trends confounding the treatment groups [33]. This method allows for the comparison of changes in innovation performance, which calculated by using the GII ranking to represent and implement NIS. The SDID quasi-experiment is conducted between countries in Asia as a treatment group and staggered by before and after the joining BRI. This research additionally observe the impact of The Special Plan for Promoting the Scientific and Technological Innovation Cooperation of the Belt and Road Construction (PSTIC) policy issued by Chinese government in 2016 [5]. The SDID approach helps isolate the impact of BRI by controlling for time-invariant differences between countries and common trends affecting all countries.

To execute this experiment, we generate two dummy variables: 1) BRI dummy variable to distinguish between treatment group (partner countries of BRI) and control group (non-partner countries of BRI); and 2) post BRI which shows when the country joins BRI and how long SDID they've become a partner country. This approach measures the economic and innovation advancement impact of BRI. In this research, the countries are divided into two groups, which is Asia and others. To further enhancing the result, income-level of the countries is divided into 4 level according to their gross net income (GNI) per capita. The following level categories are divided into: 1) low-income country \$1085 Gross National Income (GNI) in 2021; 2) lower-middle income country with GNI per capita of \$1086 - \$4255; 3) upper-middle income country with GNI per capita of \$4256 - \$13205; and 4) high-income country with GNI per capita more than \$13205.

There are two assumptions in doing SDID quasi-experiment [34] : 1) Common Trend – assuming that both the treated and control group would have the same trend indefinitely if there is no treatment or BRI PSTIC in this case; 2) Randomized Assignment – assuming that the treatment group is randomly assigned from a pool of subject. This

assumption is relevant in context of individual or group level analysis, which established the neutrality of the treatment group without the researcher’s interference. In the context of BRI and similar policy, the intervention is regarded as exogenous for the subject, hence this assumption of quasi-experiment is still valid. The SDID model used in this paper is as follows:

$$GII_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 treat_{it} * post_{it} + \beta_2 treat_{it} + \beta_3 post_{it} + \beta \sum Z_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{1}$$

Where GII is the dependent variable, GII_{it} refers to the rank of the country-i in year-t. $post_{it}$ is a dummy variable which explains when the country-i joins BRI. Before joining BRI, the corresponding year-t will gain value 0. After the year they join BRI, the dummy value assigned to $post_{it}$ will be 1. $treat_{it}$ is a sorting dummy variable to show whether country-i receives investment from BRI in year-t or not. If country-i is a partner country of BRI and receives investment in year-t, then BRI_{it} will gain the value of 1 and vice versa.

Table 1. SDID model parameters

	Before joining BRI ($post_{it} = 0$)	After joining BRI ($post_{it} = 1$)	Difference
Treatment group ($treat_{it} = 1$)	$\beta_0 + \beta_2 + \beta$	$\beta_0 + \beta_1 + \beta_2 + \beta_3 + \beta$	$\beta_1 + \beta_3$
Control group ($treat_{it} = 0$)	$\beta_0 + \beta$	$\beta_0 + \beta_3 + \beta$	β_3
Difference	β_2	$\beta_1 + \beta_2$	β_1

$treat_{it} * post_{it}$ in SDID is the interaction variables of dummy variables $post_{it}$ and sorting variables of $treat_{it}$. As shown in Table 1, the coefficient β_1 shows the real effect of implementing BRI towards the GII rank of the country. Higher coefficient and statistical importance after a certain threshold will show that the net-impact of BRI, especially in Asian partner countries. By analysing this interaction, the study will be able to answer the debatable topic of BRI importance. $\sum Z_{it}$ represents a set of control variables and ε_{it} indicates the error terms.

3.2. Data Collection

China, the initiator of BRI is geographically located in the centre of the Asia continent, specifically in East Asia [12]. This geographical condition will hypothetically bring more impact of BRI in Asian countries because the connectivity development around China will eventually help grow their connectivity towards global trade routes. Therefore, this paper will mainly use the country data of 232 countries that included in the GII rank. From those countries, 46 are located in the Asia continent, and among those Asian countries, only 5 are not part of BRI, which are: Hong Kong; India; Bhutan; Israel; and Japan.

The GII rank data is collected from “Global Innovation Index: Innovation in the Face of Uncertainty” [35]. The data of BRI investment by the Chinese government or firms is collected from “Ten years of China’s Belt and Road Initiative: Evolution and the road ahead” [36]. We use the GII dataset from the year 2011 until 2022 to measure 232 countries that have ever received BRI investment.

3.3. Measurement Variable

The underlying complexity of NIS has brought GII into the spotlight. This index is often recognized as a tool to measure the efficiency and effectiveness of a country in producing innovative actions [30]. This paper will use the rank of 127 countries as a basis for assessment rather than the more conventional way of using scores or another derivative of the scoring mechanism. Using ranking as a variable gives more emphasis on the innovation dynamic between countries and reduces the resource gap between different income levels [37]. The GII score is calculated by the following formula:

$$GII_i = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{IISI_i + IOSI_i}{n} \tag{2}$$

Where, Innovation Input Sub-Indices (IISI) is the amount of innovation input of the country, which is further divided into: institution; human capital and research; infrastructure; market sophistication; and business sophistication. Innovation Output Sub-Indices (IOSI) represents the innovation outputs of a country. IOSI consists of two parts, which are: knowledge and technology output; and creative output. IISI mainly observes the environment provided to foster innovation activity, while IOSI focuses on standardizing the outcome of innovation activity [22].

Asian continent is divided into 48 countries, and China is in the center of the mainland. The other 47 countries are either directly bordering China via land or sea, or are adjacent. Following the former journal with similar topic in natural-geographical differences, we consider countries in Asian continent as a quasi-natural selected experiment, which are geographically separated as a treatment group in the SDID model [38]. The independent dummy variables in the SDID models are: $treat_{it}$; $post_{it}$; and $treat_{it} * post_{it}$. An Asian partner country of BRI is assigned with a $treat_{it}$ value of 1. After a country becomes a partner country of BRI, the assigned value of $post_{it}$ changes into 1. Meanwhile, $treat_{it} * post_{it}$ is the SDID interaction variable (Table.1).

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
year	1776	2016.5	3.453	2011	2022
id	1776	115.973	68.133	2	232
bri	1776	0.777	0.416	0	1
asia	1778	0.304	0.46	0	1
bri inv	928	1936.175	3556.794	0	53610
total	1776	6780.462	15022.939	0	165350
hr	1602	67.732	38.765	1	143
inf	1602	67.898	38.792	1	143
mark	1602	67.985	38.869	1	163
bsn	1602	67.612	38.859	1	143
knl	1594	67.662	38.485	1	143
crt	1594	67.657	38.708	1	143
gii	1594	67.801	38.707	1	143
gnip	1754	15375.808	19732.548	230	104370
level	1755	2.856	1.032	1	5
gdp	1775	22360.339	22103.328	682	141635
briasia	1776	0.268	0.443	0	1

Control variable is a variable used for reducing the impact of unobserved factors, and more importantly to observed the direct impact of BRI towards the GII rank of a country and minimize the effect of multi-collinearity. Innovation is definitely correlated with the economic growth of a country, human capital, and international interaction [25, 39]. GII already includes part of human capital in the calculation, while this paper uses the dependent variable of GII as part of international cooperation. In order to reduce the direct impact of economic development, we designed this research to control for two variables: 1) the gross domestic product (GDP), which measures the added value of the production of goods and services; and 2) Income level, which is segmented by their GNI. To reduce the disparity between income levels of countries, we use the natural logarithm of GDP.

Result and Discussion

4.1. Descriptive Analysis

To confirm the effect of BRI towards GII rank, we first find the date of partner countries joining BRI. We then generate a dummy variable and separate this into pre and post BRI during the year of 2011 until 2022. Table 2 show the overview of the data collected. Variable Asia shown whether the country is in Asia continent or not. Variable bri_inv shows the amount and year of investment toward countries regardless they are BRI partner country or not. The following variable are part of the GII measurement: 1) IISI variables separated into hr stands for human capital and research development; inf stands for infrastructure; mark stands for market sophistication; bsn stands for business sophistication; 2) IOSI variables is separated into: knl stands for knowledge output; and crt stands for creative output.

Asia is the treatment group in this research because there is a certain amount of different condition happen in the continent that tightly related with BRI. Table 3 show the current state of Asian country in general by dividing the groups into BRI, Asia, and BRI & Asia. We can simply say that the average condition of Asian country is a little worse with the rest of the world with mean of GII of 67.885, while the other is 66.41. However, the interesting part is that BRI partner country has the tendency to be on a lower rank of GII. This condition can be observed by the average rank of non-BRI country in 23.787, while BRI country only have average rank of 80.382. Even the condition of BRI country in Asia didn't fare that different with the average GII rank of 70.616.

Table 3. Treatment group overview

Variable		No	Yes	Total
Asia	gii	67.885	66.41	67.361
	inv	1994.753	1960.192	1982.472
BRI	gii	23.787	80.382	67.361
	inv	3659.752	1481.272	1982.472
BRI & Asia	gii	65.845	70.616	67.361
	inv	1968.815	2011.792	1982.472

4.2. Baseline Estimation

According to equation (1), the baseline result for the effect of BRI on GII rank are shown in Table 4. In general, variable post shows that there are no immediate rank changes when a country only joins BRI. In line with this result, there are no effect when a country is in treat group or receiving just BRI investment across different groups. However, there is a significant negative correlation if a country is a part of BRI and receive BRI investment as shown by variable did in column one with coefficient value of -3.867 and significant at the 1% level ($P < .01$). This result shows the statistical significance of BRI towards their partner countries and how BRI investment will eventually increase the rank of the country by 3.867.

The baseline result is further explained by replacing the treatment group in column (3) and (4) from BRI partner country worldwide, into BRI partner country in Asia. While the treat and post has no significant correlation, the variable for did shows significant negative correlation with coefficient of -6.958 and significant at the 1% level ($P < .01$). Compared to column (1), the did coefficient has been increase from -3.867 to -6.958. This result show that the BRI investment would affect BRI partner country in Asia more than the rest of the world.

With the introduction of subclass control variables in column (2) and (4), there is a subtle change in did result for BRI countries in column (1) to (2), while did variable didn't have any significant changes as shown in column (3) to (4). The coefficient of did variable for BRI countries treatment group decreases from -3.867 ($P < .01$) into -3.35 ($P < .05$). This

decrease in significance level highlights the importance of economic development and country income level in assessing the worldwide effect of BRI toward the GII rank. However, the BRI partner country in Asia keeps the coefficient value from -6.985 ($P < 0.1$) and -6.704 ($P < .01$). By assessing the baseline result, we found out the significant different effect between treatment and control group. This research further examines the different consistency of result between every BRI partner country and those in the Asian continent.

Table 4. Base result

VARIABLES	(1) BRI	(2) BRI	(3) Asia	(4) asia
did	-3.867*** (-2.680)	-3.350** (-2.417)	-6.958*** (-2.786)	-6.704*** (-2.756)
treat	1.038 (0.850)	0.760 (0.647)	3.564 (1.474)	3.333 (1.452)
post	0.520 (0.428)	0.668 (0.566)	-0.0452 (-0.0428)	0.359 (0.352)
Observations	1,594	1,577	1,594	1,577
Number of id	148	148	148	148
Adjusted R-squared	0.043	0.074	0.055	0.086
Subclass FE	No	Yes	No	Yes
Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Notes: Data include all 1776 observations in 231 countries in GII rank. Robust standard errors clustered at the subclass level parentheses.

*** Significant at the 1 percent level.

**Significant at the 5 percent level.

*Significant at the 10 percent level.

As shown in Fig.1, Asian BRI partner country is generally having lower starting rank compared to the others and enjoying higher degree of increase in GII rank compared to BRI partner country and non-BRI country. In Fig.1 (A), both treatment and control group have similar stable pattern in 2012 until 2014, but BRI countries show significant increase in rank in 2015 approaching the PSTIC in 2016. From Fig.1 (B), we were able to see similar pattern in the beginning of 2011 but started to change trajectory in the opening of BRI in 2013. In 2016, the BRI-Asia treatment group show sharp increase in their GII rank. Overall, this result show consistent result with several previous studies [14, 40].

Fig.1. BRI impact toward GII rank

4.3. Temporal Effect

As a follow-up of the previous discussion related to the BRI impact in different periods, we design a model of DID regulated order of temporal effect. This model can show the treatment effect in the different time span or period and discern the probability of missing observation [41]. We separate the observation into 5 phases: 1) before BRI; 2) after BRI; 3) before PSTIC; and 4) after PSTIC. The equation for temporal effects is as follow:

$$GII_{it} = \beta_0 + \sum_{j=2013}^{-2} \beta_j treat_{it} * post_j + \sum_{k=2013}^9 \beta_k treat_{it} * post_j + \sum_{l=2016}^{-5} \beta_l treat_{it} * post_j + \sum_{m=2016}^6 \beta_m treat_{it} * post_j + \beta \sum Z_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \tag{3}$$

Table 5 shows the different phases with two big events, which are the announcement of BRI in 2013 and PSTIC in 2016. Phase 1 didn't have significance because BRI just announced in 2013. Phase 2 show did coefficient of -5.517 (P< .05), which show the statistically significant effect of BRI in increasing the GII rank by 5.517. This increase is similar with the countries who join before 2016 in phase 3 with did coefficient of -5.85 (P< .05). However, there is no significance correlation after the PSTIC introduced in 2016. In summary, the temporal effect shows that the biggest changes for DID treatment group happen after 2013 and before 2016. This result explains the huge significance of BRI investment after its establishment in 2013, by joining and receiving the BRI investment, partner is expected to increase their GII rank by 5.517. However, this condition didn't last after 2016. This condition might occur because of unobserved variables or condition, especially covid-19.

Table 5. Temporal effect

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
VARIABLES	Pooled OLS	Phase 1	Phase 2	Phase 3	Phase 4
did	-6.704*** (-2.756)	-0.381 (-0.0355)	-5.517** (-2.003)	-5.850** (-2.299)	-1.726 (-0.850)
treat	3.333 (1.452)	2.560 (1.125)	2.682 (0.974)	2.847 (1.196)	0.00863 (0.00413)
post	0.359 (0.352)	1.410 (0.271)	0.643 (0.633)	-0.393 (-0.283)	2.339** (2.501)
Observations	1,577	408	1,310	818	887
Number of ids	148	143	148	146	137
Adjusted R-squared	0.086	0.065	0.094	0.055	0.026
Subclass FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year Fixed Effect	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Robust t-statistics in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

4.4. Robustness Test

Ordinal scale is discontinuous data which vulnerable against skewedness caused by unnatural distribution. However, there is few studies who believe that ordinal scale after some extent were able to display similar result to continuous scale data [42]. This paper uses the ordinal scale as robustness test to test the sensitivity of the data compared to continuous scale data. To execute the test, we divide the GII rank data according to the percentile of the whole data.

Table 6. Ordinal Scale Test

VARIABLES	(1) BRI	(2) BRI	(3) Asia	(4) asia
did	-0.466*** (-4.246)	-0.479*** (-4.300)	-0.295** (-2.171)	-0.504*** (-3.638)
treat	0.361*** (5.008)	0.416*** (5.656)	0.0330 (0.341)	0.518*** (5.142)
post	0.304*** (3.531)	0.346*** (3.959)	0.233*** (3.023)	0.255*** (3.249)
Observations	1,776	1,775	1,776	1,775
Subclass Fixed Effect	No	Yes	No	Yes
Year Fixed Effect	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

z-statistics in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 7. Subsample analysis: income level

VARIABLES	(1) OLS pool	(2) 1	(3) 2	(4) 3	(5) 4
did	-6.913*** (-2.863)	-12.91*** (-4.695)	-11.14** (-2.635)	-10.21** (-2.422)	0.801 (0.368)
treat	3.416 (1.377)	15.00*** (6.145)	3.624 (1.246)	3.961 (0.984)	0.687 (0.353)
post	-0.0596 (-0.0563)	-2.143 (-0.920)	4.001 (1.537)	-0.243 (-0.119)	1.335 (1.179)
Observations	1,593	167	401	416	609
Number of id	148	22	50	52	66
Adjusted R-squared	0.067	0.250	0.269	0.075	0.095
Subclass Fixed Effect	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year Fixed Effect	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Robust t-statistics in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 6 show the regression result of 10 sorting dummy GII rank groups variable. The result shows that almost every result become statistically significant at 1% level. To compare it with the base result (see Table.4), there is a change in did result on column (2), from 5% significance into 1% significance; and (3), from 1% significance to 5% significance. This result shows the possibility of skewedness in the data into certain tolerable extent. The changes might be the result of uneven changes between ranks, where lower rank data is relatively easier to be overtook compared to the higher one, thus lowering the possibility to cross the percentile [43].

Subsample analysis or stratified test is a common method in psychological journal. The main purpose is splitting the observation data into categories or sub-classes [44]. In this paper, we use stratified analysis as a basis in assessing

possible heterogeneity of the overall condition of the base result. Subsample analysis is able to provide the heterogeneity among classes and between classes [45]. The largest differences between classes in this study is represented by the economic power of the country. In order to capture this possible heterogenous variable, the classes will be divided by the income level of countries according to their GNI.

Table 7 show the stratified analysis of countries in Asia according to their income level. The overview of the overall result is as follows: 1) low-income level with coefficient of -11.76 ($P < .05$); 2) lower-middle income level with coefficient level of -8.765 ($P < .01$); 3) higher-middle income level with coefficient level of -9.336 ($P < 0.5$); 4) BRI investment had no significant effect toward high-income level countries. In summary, the BRI investment is able to increase the ranking of low-income level countries by 11.76 unit and significant throughout the other level such as lower-middle and upper-middle level countries. However, this effect doesn't include high-income level countries, hypothetically because: 1) only a handful of high-income level country that is part of BRI, such as Korea, Senegal, and Saudi Arabia; 2) The impact might be diminished by the amount of economic power of high-income level countries.

Discussion, Implication, Limitation and Future Research, and Conclusion

5.1 Discussion

To discern the effect of international policy, particularly the BRI, on the effectiveness of NIS, this study employed a SDID quasi-experimental design. The SDID approach provided a robust framework to control for time-invariant differences between countries and common trends affecting all countries, thereby isolating the impact of BRI on innovation performance, as measured by the GII. The findings reveal that BRI investment significantly enhances the GII rank of partner countries, with the effect being more pronounced in Asian countries. Although the biggest winner of BRI is Asian country, BRI partner in other continent also receives improvement. This improvement was particularly notable from the announcement of BRI in 2013 until the introduction of PSTIC policy in 2016. The temporal analysis indicated that the positive impact was strongest during this period, suggesting that the initial phase of BRI implementation had the most substantial influence.

To prevent the possibility of skewedness and sensitive data, this research provides ordinal percentile scale robustness test as a countermeasure. Furthermore, this research also incorporates the stratified analysis, where the regression group is segregated according to the income level of the country. The ordinal scale test indicated that the impact of BRI remained significant even when the GII rank data was categorized into percentiles, highlighting the robustness of the findings against potential data skewness and the data is safe from sensitivity bias. The subsample analysis demonstrated that low and middle-income countries experienced more significant benefits from BRI investments compared to high-income countries. This result highlighting the huge impact of BRI that purposefully helping lower income country in developing their NIS and underscore the differential impact based on economic status.

5.2 Practical Implication

This study enriches the theoretical landscape surrounding NIS by illustrating how international policies like the BRI can act as significant external catalysts for innovation. By integrating the GII as a measurement tool, our findings incorporate the traditional innovation theories that emphasize endogenous factors and shed light to the exogenous influences, especially large-scale international collaborations. This contribution advances the theoretical framework of NIS, particularly in the context of using specific indices to represent the NIS.

In a practical context, the research provides actionable insights for policymakers and business leaders navigating the global economic landscape. Policymakers in BRI-participating countries can leverage these findings to align national development strategies with international initiatives, optimizing resource allocation to enhance innovation performance. For businesses, especially within Asia, the BRI opens avenues for strategic positioning by capitalizing on improved infrastructure and connectivity, thereby enhancing competitiveness and accessing new markets. Furthermore, the study highlights the significant benefits of targeted investments for low and middle-income countries, guiding

international organizations and development agencies in directing resources towards this economic and innovation growth.

5.3 Limitation and Future Research

The research using the data from 2011 until 2023 and only focus on the economic and innovation improvement without taking much consideration on cultural and geopolitical effect of BRI. The future impact of BRI, especially in a cultural and political term has always been an ambiguity. In order to answer that, the continuation purpose of the initiative should be further understood, and future research should explore the long-term sustainability of these impacts and investigate the factors contributing to the diminished effects observed post-2016. Additionally, studies in other regions could provide further insights into the global applicability of these findings.

5.4 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study provides compelling evidence that international policy initiatives like the BRI can significantly enhance national innovation systems, particularly in regions with geographical and economical alignment with the policy's objectives. The findings suggest that targeted international investments can play a crucial role in fostering innovation and economic development, especially in developing regions. This result should give a consideration for government in selecting partner in a global scale. Because, innovation scale up varieties of the country power, from human resources, productivity, to economic advancement.

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